

THE IMPORTANCE OF TEACHING PRONUNCIATION

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Pronunciation refers to the way words are spoken. With the ability of pronunciation, everyone will be able to pronounce words correctly while speaking in English and will be able to gain self-confidence to speak in English. Proper pronunciation can be defined as a reproduction of language sounds in such a way that the intended message is passed easily. The exact meaning of pronunciation is how word is pronounced. If we change in pronunciation, the meaning will be changed. Pronunciation is the production of sounds that we use to make meaning. It includes attention to the particular sounds of a language (segments), such as intonation, syllable, phrasing, stress, timing, rhythm how the voice is projected (voice quality) and attention to gestures and expressions that are closely related to the way we speak a language. A broad definition of pronunciation includes both suprasegmental and segmental features. These all features work in combination when we speak, and are therefore usually pronunciation as an integral part of spoken language.

Cook states that Pronunciation is a set of habits of producing sounds. The habit of producing a sound is acquired by repeating it over and over again and by being corrected when it is pronounced wrongly. Learning to pronounce a second language means building up new pronunciation habits and overcoming the bias of the first language.

Pronunciation plays an important role in English speaking to express our ideas. English is not native language for everyone and hence the pronunciation of Indian speakers of English is different from that of the native speaker. Some speakers of the English language attract us with their good command of English language. It is their pronunciations that leave impact on us as listeners. It is an essential part of every speaker to speak with the right pronunciation. Since we are not native speakers of English, there exists a very serious problem with regard to the pronunciation of the Indian speaker's English. English is widespread language. Because of a variety of English spoken in different parts of the world, there is no purity of pronunciation. Therefore, we often come across alternate pronunciation and mispronunciations. However, no matter how common the incorrect pronunciation is, people always need to strive to acquire correct pronunciation.

Many people learning and speaking English language often do not pay any attention to their pronunciation. Some of them underestimate it and ignore it.

They think that pronunciation is not as important as speaking and pronunciation is less important than grammar and vocabulary. But the fact is that pronunciation is extremely important. In many cases of misunderstanding in communication were caused by the mispronouncing of words or the improper intonation. For example, if someone pronounces the words fog and fox, see and she, sick and six with relatively no differences, in some cases can lead to a misunderstanding. Another example: when one pronounces the word present with stress in the first syllable, whereas she uses in the sentence "I'd like to present" is certainly incorrect and irritating. In addition, good pronunciation can also give a plus value to those who master it. People get amazed of your English language when they hear you speaking in English and thinking about your pronunciation skill? The answer is the quality of the pronunciation. Good pronunciation skill can give you more self-confidence when you speak in front of many people. So, it has become more and more obvious that pronunciation cannot be underestimated. It must become one's priority while he/she is learning English. At least, the learners of English should give the same proportion of time and attention to pronunciation as they do to grammar and vocabulary.

The teaching of pronunciation in Second Language classes has become an important element in order to achieve an intelligible communication and to improve children' oral competences. Most of the English teachers and Non-native English Teachers (from now on NNETs) overlook pronunciation as they focus their teaching in other English areas, which are deemed to be more important. Even though, one of the key requirement for language proficiency is to secure understandable pronunciation for the language learners (Gilakjani, 2012). Researchers and teachers would all agree that being competent in the Language is an essential condition for any Language teacher. Furthermore, in recent years, there has been a significant demand for English teachers as schools have introduced and increased the number of teaching hours for foreign languages, mainly English. This latter fact have caused Non-native Speaker Teachers go abroad to improve their Foreign Language skills. The following lines will provide a general and brief overview of the literature focused on the importance of pronunciation, pronunciation instruction and the perceptions teachers present during pronunciation instruction in their classrooms. Furthermore, the reasons why pronunciation awareness is fundamental to develop communicative abilities and to avoid mispronunciation will also be presented.

The purpose of this section is to present and analyse the role of

pronunciation during Non-native English Teachers practices throughout the historical research. Several studies such as Macdonald (2002) and Baker (2014) reveal that either the deficit of pronunciation' awareness, or the amount of reluctant teachers still remain in Foreign Language classrooms. Also, the communicative elements are not quite implemented in Foreign Language Teaching practices. These facts seem to be caused due to the fact that teachers lack knowledge of what to teach and how to carry it out, as well as, suitable high quality teaching and learning materials are still insufficient nowadays.

Reference.

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